

Artificial Neural Networks: Paving the way to Next Generation Healthcare and Research

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Abstract– The latest and most interesting development in the field of Deep Learning (DL) is an artificial neural network (ANN). An ANN mimics the organization and functionality of the human brain. The ANNs also tend to learn from the data that is fed to them and utilize that information for future analyses. ANNs have been extensively used in various fields including computer vision, speech recognition, natural language processing, bioinformatics, drug design, and machine translations. It is just recently that ANNs are being utilized to solve problems in the field of healthcare and scientific research. Encapsulating a broad spectrum of applications of ANN in these domains, this review focuses on the recent developments that have been made possible by understanding the approach of using the machine learning model. A discussion about the scope and possibilities of ANN in these domains has been provided to shed light on this powerful technology in the scientific community.

Keywords– Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Brain-Computer Interface (BCI), Deep Learning (DL), Support Vector Machine (SVM).

I. INTRODUCTION

The human brain is one of the biggest mysteries of the living world. The fundamental unit of electrical conduction in it is the highly modified type of cell called a neuron. It is the extensive and intricate interactions among billions of such neurons that make it possible for the brain to perceive, analyze, and calculate a biological input (called stimulus) in such an intelligent manner. Although replicating such machinery in a non-living entity seems impossible, great strides in technology have led to the development of

mechanisms that *think* like the human brain. These mechanisms are computational machine learning algorithms that, unlike conventional algorithms, tend to learn from the input data and utilize that information for analysis of subsequent data. The latest and most interesting development in the field of Deep Learning (DL) is an artificial neural network (ANN). An ANN mimics the organization and functionality of the human brain. Just like the neurons form an interconnected network and produce output only when the input reaches a threshold level, an ANN also consists of units or nodes (called artificial neurons) that are interconnected and that produce output only when the input reaches a pre-defined threshold magnitude [2]. The ANNs also tend to learn from the data that is fed to them and utilize that information for future analyses. Therefore, the more data an ANN processes, the more intelligent it gets, and higher will be its computational and predictive accuracy.

Since its implementation in mid-2010, ANNs have been extensively used in various fields including computer vision, speech recognition, natural language processing, bioinformatics, drug design, and machine translations, to name a few. However, its application in the field of healthcare and scientific research is merely beginning. The medical sector is rapidly evolving, incorporating novel strategies to diagnose and treat various human diseases. At the same time, scientific research is making use of newer methods and techniques to study both existing knowledge and newly discovered information. An important aspect of such progress is the accurate prediction of the outcomes if the variables are known. The ANNs therefore, possess tremendous scope of application in these areas. In this review article, we go through some of the major applications of ANN in the fields of healthcare and scientific research and understand the approach of using the technology in these domains.

II. APPLICATIONS

A. Prediction of operons

Currently, there are two ways for the prediction of operon, Neighbouring gene pair prediction model (NGPP) method and the Gene cluster prediction (GCP) method. While the NGPP method is convenient, simple, and accurate, it fails for single-gene operons. On the other hand, the GCP method applies to single-gene operons and has robust identification. However, it is highly complex and inconvenient for computation. Therefore, an operon prediction model has been designed using ANN. This model showed high accuracy, sensitivity, versatility, and applies to all types of operons. It can also be used to predict newly identified operons [6].

B. Prediction of chronic kidney disease

Chronic kidney disease can lead to kidney failure in the late stages. Diabetes, high blood pressure, and unhealthy lifestyles have led to an increase in the number of patients with CKD. So, it has become necessary to devise models that can predict CKD at an early stage. Machine learning techniques such as an artificial neural network (ANN) and support vector machine (SVM) have been used to build CKD prediction models. Using 11 numerical attributes (such as age, blood pressure, blood glucose, etc.) and 13 nominal attributes (such as albumin, sugar, RBCs, etc.), ANN and SVM could predict CKD at early stages with accuracies of 99.75% and 97.75%, respectively [9]. Since ANN has a higher tendency to learn and predict, it has the scope of being a very accurate model for the prediction of CKD.

C. Identification of specific oligonucleotides

Identification of oligonucleotides that are specific for processes such as DNA microarray, PCR, and mRNA silencing is very important. Oligos have been identified and designed in various ways such as frequency matrix, information-theoretical method, frequency of sequence landscapes, suffix trees, and smart filtering technique [4]. However, all these methods still take a long time to identify specific oligos. By integrating ANN with BLAST (Basic Local Alignment Search Tool), an IAB (Integration of ANN and BLAST) algorithm was developed. The IAB algorithm performed 5.2, 7.1, and 6.7 times faster than the BLAST search without ANN for 70-mer, 50-mer, and 25-mer specific oligos, respectively [4]. These results were proofread by

PCR. Thus, ANN could tremendously enhance the speed and specificity of identifying genome-wide oligos.

D. Prediction of fold resistance

Fold resistance refers to the increase in resistance of the pathogen against a particular drug. Prediction of fold resistance of HIV-1, subtype B (being, the most common) is essential to any treatment or therapy with anti-retroviral drugs. Addressing these issues, several prediction algorithms have been devised by different research groups such as REGA, ANRS, HIVdb, SVM-based geno2pheno tool, multi-label classification, and SVM variants, amongst others. To enhance the accuracy and scope of predictability, a regression ANN has been used to design a constantly-learning prediction algorithm. For each of the eight protease inhibitors, six nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors, and four non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors, their algorithm produced high mean R^2 values, low variance, and competitive classification procedures [10]. As such, the ANN proved to be a tremendous boost to the performance of the prediction algorithm.

E. Estimation of sodium absorption ratio

Sodium absorption ratio (SAR) is the concentration of sodium ions relative to the total concentration of calcium and magnesium ions. Mathematically, SAR is represented as:

$$SAR = \frac{[Na]}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}([Ca]+[Mg])}} \quad [11]$$

Generally, the higher the SAR, the less is the suitability of the water for agricultural and domestic use. When an artificial neural network was created with pH, sulfate, chloride, and electrical conductivity as input variables, ANN proves to be a helpful and exact tool for predicting the amount of SAR in ground-water resources of Aras catchment area (located in Azerbaijan). These results were far superior to those obtained by multiple linear regressions [7].

F. Prediction of protein subcellular location

Prediction of protein location within the cell is an important step in the functional characterization of proteins. There are two main techniques by which protein subcellular location is determined from its structure. One technique involves deducing all those protein motifs or structures that are characteristic of a particular signal molecule or ligand of the target location. The other technique employs the determination of homology between the protein and other proteins of known locations. However, both these techniques

rely on the availability of the exact protein sequence as well as information about all signal or carrier molecules. A third technique has been developed wherein the physicochemical environment of the exposed amino acids is compared to that of the different target locations. By combining an SVM (trained with this information) with an ANN, the locations of a large number of proteins could be deduced accurately. Proteins with high homology but different locations could also be predicted using this algorithm [3].

G. Lifestyle improvement of big stroke patients

There are millions of people who suffer from big stroke annually [1]. Big stroke refers to the sudden interruption of blood supply to the brain rendering part or all of the body paralyzed. Such patients are often provided with complex systems powered by brain-computer interfaces (BCI) for their day-to-day activities. However, the efficiency of the BCI in processing and classifying the brain signals depends on the algorithm powering the BCI. When Discrete Wavelength Transform (DWT) was used as a feature extraction tool, ANN showed the highest classification accuracy of 95.24%. When using Principal Components Analysis (PCA) as a feature extraction tool, ANN again showed the highest classification accuracy of 92.86% [1]. This proved that ANN-based BCIs perform significantly better than SVM and LDA (Linear Discriminant Analysis)-based classifiers.

H. *In silico* drug and vaccine development

Dengue is an acute disease mainly endemic to the tropical and sub-tropical regions. Due to the rapidly mutating dengue virus and lack of information regarding its pathogenesis in humans, drugs and vaccines cannot be easily designed against it. However, modern computational methods such as ANN and hidden Markov model (HMM) are being used for *in silico* design of drugs and vaccines. For drug designing, the NS3 protease (pro)enzyme is required to be modeled. However, the crystal structure of a related NS3 protease from the Hepatitis C virus was used as a model. For vaccine development, the envelop proteins E DENV-2 and E DENV-3 were used as models due to their prevalence in South East Asia. The ANN was used to predict the best possible interactions between NS3 protease and its substrate to deduce a substrate-inhibitor drug design. Simultaneously, the ANN could show the possible response of the human immune system to the vaccine [14]. This technique can be extended to other types of biomedical research as well.

I. Prediction of phenotype from genotypic data

The human population contains a large number of variations and hence, determining the phenotype from gene expression data often becomes inaccurate. In recent years, several machine learning techniques have been used to do the same. However, their inconsistencies and randomized results have prevented their application in the clinical field. Recently, a GRRANN (Gene Regulatory Network-based Regularized Artificial Neural Network) has been designed by [13] using data on the actual interactions of the genes with their regulatory proteins. When they tested their algorithm in predicting clinical outcomes using clinical trial data on acute rejection in kidney transplantation and response to Infliximab in ulcerative colitis, they found that integrating biological knowledge before classification significantly improves the robustness and generalizability of the predictions to independent datasets [13].

J. Prediction of metastasis of cancer cells

Cancer cells show a unique property termed metastasis wherein the cells migrate from the point of origin to other regions. Metastasis of breast cancer cells can directly lead to the death of breast cancer patients [15]. Although several biomarkers of such cells have been studied to determine the metastatic state, the accuracy of such methods in predicting the metastasis is fairly low. This is mainly attributed to inconsistencies among patients, types of cancers, and partial epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition states (EMT). However, the use of computer vision through microfluidic single-cell migration chip and high-content imaging to derive certain key morphological changes that occur during metastasis has proved to be highly fruitful. Using a Random Decision Forest (RDF) and an ANN to train the algorithm, cancer cell migration direction could be predicted with over 99% accuracy and migration speed with over 91% accuracy [15].

K. Prediction of genetic values

The genetic value of a breed of an animal refers to the effect of the genes of the animal on its production. Predicting the genetic value during breeding programs is an important step in ensuring the success of the program. Several procedures based on linear models have been used for this purpose however, their accuracy has not been satisfactory. When an ANN was trained and used for this purpose, the predictive accuracy and network efficiency were enhanced. In 75% of the scenarios, ANN proved to be more effective than the least-

squares method in the attainment of genetic values [5]. Therefore, integrating ANNs into the prediction algorithms can provide significantly better results than conventional procedures.

L. Diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a mental disorder characterized by a progressive decline in memory and important mental functions. Currently, it is a global health crisis due to its increasing incidences [8]. Extensive research on AD has led to the discovery of certain biomarkers for diagnosing the disease. However, they cannot be used to predict the development of AD at an early stage. Few computational methods based on ANN have been developed however, they make use of invasive clinical examinations or complex laboratory tests as input variables, which may not be practical while screening large populations. The ANN model, which has been recently developed, makes use of demographic and behavioral characteristics, medical history, neuropsychological performance, and biomarkers as inputs. As such, it is quite practical and inexpensive for use in mass screening programs. The model could achieve an average sensitivity of 87.28%, a specificity of 94.74%, and an accuracy of 92.13% with an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.897 [8].

III. CONCLUSION

The applications mentioned in the preceding section are just the tip of the deep iceberg of the utilizations of ANN possible in these domains of study. Understanding the problems and recurring issues in these fields is central to the development of approaches that can be undertaken to solve them with ANNs. Research and discovery are a dynamic process. New things are discovered, and unknown mysteries are unfolded every day. Thus, the scope and use of ANN will go on increasing with time. With more amount of data being fed to the ANNs, the machine learning model will keep on getting *smarter* with time. The accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity of its predictions will also go on increasing with time. Incorporation of ANNs into the biomedical sector, as cited in the "Applications" section, has already brought radical progress in disease prognosis, diagnosis, and subsequently, treatment and prevention. Its integration into the various prediction tools used in different fields of scientific research has significantly enhanced the quality of the results produced by scientists all over the world. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is

believed to be the next big thing in the history of the technological progress of mankind, and ANN plays a huge role in it. It is just a matter of time that ANNs become the sought-after tool for prediction and analysis in the entire field of science.

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V. REFERENCES

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